

PREPREG DEVELOPMENT FOR RAPID ON-ORBIT COMPOSITES MANUFACTURING VIA FRONTAL CURING

Tyler Price¹, Po-Wen Wang², Jeffrey Moore³, Sameh Tawfick⁴, and Nancy Sottos⁵

¹Beckman Institute for Advanced Science & Technology and Department of Materials Science & Engineering, Grainger College of Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
3307 Beckman Institute, 405 N Mathews Ave, Urbana, IL, 61801, USA
Email: tylercp2@illinois.edu, web page: <https://sottosgroup.matse.illinois.edu/people/tyler-price>

²Beckman Institute for Advanced Science & Technology and Department of Materials Science & Engineering, Grainger College of Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
3300 Beckman Institute, 405 N Mathews Ave, Urbana, IL, 61801, USA
Email: powenww2@illinois.edu, web page: <https://sottosgroup.matse.illinois.edu/people/po-wen-wang>

³Beckman Institute for Advanced Science & Technology and Department of Chemistry, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
3351 Beckman Institute, 405 N Mathews Ave, Urbana, IL, 61801, USA
Email: jsmoore@illinois.edu, web page: <https://chemistry.illinois.edu/jsmoore>

⁴Beckman Institute for Advanced Science & Technology and Department of Mechanical Science & Engineering, Grainger College of Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
4412 Mechanical Engineering Lab, 105 S Mathews Ave, Urbana, IL, 61801, USA
Email: tawfick@illinois.edu, web page: <https://mechse.illinois.edu/people/profile/tawfick>

⁵Beckman Institute for Advanced Science & Technology and Department of Materials Science & Engineering, Grainger College of Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
203 Materials Science & Engineering Building, 1304 W Green St, Urbana, IL, 61801, USA
Email: n-sottos@illinois.edu, web page: <https://matse.illinois.edu/people/profile/n-sottos>

Keywords: Prepreg, Thermosetting resin, Cure, Thermal analysis, Cure behavior, Carbon fibre

ABSTRACT

We develop a novel A-staging approach for manufacturing a stable, frontally curable prepreg, to address the challenges of in-space composite manufacturing. The prepreg achieves room temperature stability through two key innovations: (1) physical separation of the reactive components via microencapsulation of the polymerization initiator and (2) the use of unreacted monomer (i.e. A-stage) resins that are solid at room temperature. A two-step dip-coating and infusion process was developed to manufacture the prepreg. Systematic studies of the dip-coating process reveal predictable and repeatable microparticle uptake that varies linearly with the dip-coating suspension concentration. Leveraging these results, we demonstrate control over the resin composition by achieving a desired initiator:monomer ratio in the prepreg despite introducing them in separate steps. When properly packaged, the prepreg remains below 20% conversion for at least 30 days at room temperature and pressure—a 300-fold improvement in shelf-life compared to B-staged DCPD prepreps.

1 INTRODUCTION

Large space structures, such as the international space station, are currently assembled in space from terrestrially manufactured components. This approach imposes mass and deployment constraints that limit the scale and robustness of space infrastructure.[1, 2] In-space manufacturing (ISM) offers a transformative paradigm to reduce the cost and increase the scale of space structures.[3, 4]

Continuous fiber reinforced composites are well-suited for ISM due to their high specific strength and stiffness.[5-7] However, current composite manufacturing methods and materials are poorly suited

for ISM due to their complex tooling, multi-step processing, energy intensive curing, and/or reactive feedstocks with limited shelf-life. Thermoset prepregs pose the most promising pathway to ISM of composites by eliminating the complexity of resin mixing and infusion on-orbit. A typical thermoset prepreg consists of reinforcement pre-impregnated with resin that is partially gelled or “B-staged.”[8, 9] Conventional prepregs such as Hexcel’s M21 or Toray’s 3960 require high temperature, multi-hour cure cycles and must be stored at sub-ambient temperatures to achieve storage lives longer than 2 months.[10, 11] Highly reactive “snap-cure” prepregs such as Hexcel’s M77 series reduce cycle time but suffer from very short shelf-lives, up to 2 months at 0°C, which are incompatible with 6-month launch timelines.[12] New prepreg systems are needed for ISM that combine long term stability at room temperature with rapid, low-energy curing.

Frontal curing (FC) offers a pathway towards stability and rapid conversion of monomer. Frontal curing leverages the heat of polymerization to generate a self-sustaining polymerization front that passes through the material.[13-15] A front can be initiated using a small local stimulus (e.g. UV, heat) which consumes 10^5 to 10^{10} less energy than conventional oven cures.[16] Frontally curable epoxy- and olefin-based resins have found success in composites manufacturing via additive, vacuum infusion, and wet layup methods, though these pose substantial risk for ISM.[17-24]

Shelf-stable FC prepregs remain elusive due to the limited pot life of formulated resins; Parikh developed the first FC prepreg material using dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) resin but found 80% conversion after 8h at room temperature or 14 days at -20°C, likely due to degradation of the phosphite inhibitor.[24, 25] More recently, Davydovich et al. achieved 8 months of stability at room temperature in unreinforced DCPD resins by microencapsulating the polymerization initiator (Hoveyda-Grubbs Second-Generation Catalyst).[26] However, the microencapsulation strategy precludes B-staging as the sequestered Grubbs-type catalyst remains inactive until thermally triggered release, at which point frontal curing begins immediately.

In this work, we introduce a novel frontally curable DCPD prepreg system tailored for ISM of carbon fiber composites. The prepreg (Figure 1) leverages polysulfone-encapsulated Grubbs’ Second-Generation Catalyst (G2) and unreacted (i.e. A-stage) monomer that is solid at room temperature. We develop the manufacturing process for this A-stage prepreg and evaluate prepreg stability as well as cured composite performance as a function of storage time at room-temperature.

Figure 1: Microparticle Prepreg Strategy. The proposed “A-stage” prepreg material combines high purity endo-dicyclopentadiene resin, which is solid at room temperature, with polysulfone encapsulated Grubbs’ Second-Generation Catalyst (G2) to achieve long term stability at ambient

temperature while enabling low-energy on-demand curing via frontal curing due to the thermally triggered release of G2 from the microparticles.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Constituent Materials

Endo-dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) was purchased from Cymetech Corporation (UltreneTM 99, >99%, $T_m=32-34^\circ\text{C}$). Grubbs' Second-Generation Catalyst (G2) was purchased from Chemscone Corporation. Polysulfone (PSU) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Corporation. Poly(ethylene-alt-maleic anhydride) (EMA) was purchased from Aurorium (ZemaCTM E400). Dichloromethane was purchased from Fischer Scientific. All chemicals were used as received without further purification. The reinforcing phase consisted of 5 plies of T300 2x2 twill weave carbon fiber fabric from Rock West Composites (1300D, 3K tow, 204 g/m²). The fabric was cut to size (100 mm x 125 mm) and dried in an oven at 110°C for at least 2 hours to remove residual moisture. The plies were cooled and stored in a desiccator prior to use.

2.2 Catalyst Microparticle Preparation and Characterization

PSU microparticles containing G2 (PSU-G2) were manufactured using an oil-in-water emulsion technique similar to the work of Davydovich *et al.*[26] The oil phase was prepared using dichloromethane (56mL), PSU (5g), and G2 (0.7g), and the aqueous phase (200mL) was prepared with the EMA surfactant (7.6g). After emulsification using a homogenizer, the solvent was removed by evaporation. The microparticle-containing emulsion was centrifuged, and the supernatant was decanted. After two subsequent aqueous washing steps to remove EMA, the microparticles were freeze-dried to yield a free-flowing light pink powder (Figure 2A, ~4g, ~70% yield).

Figure 2. Microparticle Characterization. (A) Image of the PSU-G2 microparticles. Scale bar (black) 1 cm. (B) SEM image of PSU-G2 microparticles after applying an edge detection algorithm to determine microparticle size distribution. Green circles represent detected edges and red denotes the centroid. Scale bar (white) 10 μm. (C) Histogram of microparticle diameter from automated edge detection applied to SEM images with log-normal fit.

¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) was used to determine the average mass ratio of G2 to PSU in microparticles. NMR was conducted on a Bruker CB500. Spectra are referenced to residual CDCl₃ ($\delta=7.26$ ppm), with chemical shifts reported in parts per million. The molar ratio of G2 to PSU repeat units was determined by comparing the integration of the peaks corresponding to the benzylidene proton from G2 ($\delta=19.15$ ppm) against the four aromatic protons from polysulfone ($\delta=7.84$ ppm). The mass ratio G2/PSU was calculated from the molar ratio using the molar masses of G2 (848.98 g/mol) and the polysulfone repeat unit (472.60 g/mol).

The morphology and size distribution of the PSU-G2 microparticles were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM samples were coated with Au/Pd using a Denton Desk II TSC turbo-pumped sputter coater. SEM was performed on a FEI Quanta 450 FEG. The size of individual

PSU-G2 microparticles was measured by applying a custom Hough-circle-transform-based Python script to detect particle edges in the SEM images (Figure 2B).

The PSU-G2 microparticle preparation method produced microparticles with narrower size distribution and lower initiator loading compared to prior work. Replicate preparations exhibited slight variability in G2 loading with average G2/PSU mass ratios of 0.024 and 0.042. In contrast, Davydovich *et al.* reported a higher loading of 0.105 using Hoveyda-Grubbs' Second-Generation Catalyst, which could be due to differences in catalyst structure or encapsulation process.[26] To evaluate particle size, we analyzed SEM images using a custom Hough circle transformation algorithm to identify ca. 220 particles. The resulting size histogram (Figure 2C) follows a log-normal distribution with high correlation. The median particle diameter was 1.34 μm with standard deviation 0.35 μm , representing a significantly narrower distribution than prior work.[26] Moreover, the maximum microparticle diameter was also much smaller in this study. In this work, none exceeded the fiber diameter whereas the largest particles in prior studies exceeded the diameter of carbon fiber.

2.3 Prepreg and Composite Characterization

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed in triplicate on prepreg samples and cured laminates at each time point in the longitudinal study. DSC was conducted using a TA Instruments Discovery DSC 2500 on 4-7 mg samples in Tzero pans. Cure kinetics experiments were conducted on prepreg samples from 0-200°C at 10°C/min. Heat-cool-heat post-cure DSC cycles were performed on cured composite samples from 0-250°C at 10°C/min. For both cure kinetics and post-cure DSC, the polymerization exotherm was measured over the range of 50-150°C using TA Trios software. The measured exotherm was corrected for reinforcement mass by burning off the matrix of the DSC samples in a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) similar to ASTM D3171 Method I Procedure H.[28] TGA was also conducted on unreinforced polymer to account for carbonization of the matrix as described in the standard. TGA was conducted on a TA Instruments Q500 in platinum pans with a 10°C/min ramp to 600°C and 30-min isothermal hold at 600°C. The degree of cure α was calculated for prepreps and cured laminates using Equation 1 where H_{res} is the observed residual exotherm corrected for reinforcement mass and H_r is the total enthalpy of reaction determined from a freshly prepared prepreg sample corrected for reinforcement mass.

$$\alpha = 1 - H_{res}/H_r \quad (1)$$

Soxhlet extractions were also performed on cured laminates at each point in the longitudinal study to determine the soluble fraction of the cured material. While the DSC provides a reactivity-based measure of curing, extraction provides a mass-based assessment of incorporation which provides valuable insights for space qualification where residual volatile material and off-gassing are critical considerations though the technique is no substitute for thermal vacuum characterization.[29] The extractions were performed under nitrogen over 20h on 25 mm x 50 mm cured samples using dichloromethane (DCM) heated to 65°C. This procedure was selected over the 4h 260°C procedure described in ASTM C613 to minimize the effects of oxidative crosslinking at elevated temperatures which could lead to under-estimation of the unincorporated mass fraction.[30]

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed on cured laminates during the longitudinal study to characterize their thermomechanical performance. DMA was conducted on a TA Instruments RSA-G2 in a 3-point bend configuration using the provided fixture with a 25mm span. Samples were cut and polished to 30 mm x 5 mm x ~1.1 mm. An oscillation heat ramp was applied at 2°C/min from 20-250°C with dynamic loading of 0.01% strain amplitude at 1 Hz. All experiments were conducted in a nitrogen environment. The average glass transition temperature T_g was taken as the peak of the $\tan\delta$ curve determined using TA Trios software for $n=2$ samples. The reported error is the range of values. The fiber volume fraction V_f for each laminate in the longitudinal study was characterized according to ASTM D3171 Method II using Equation 2 where n is the number of plies (5), h is the average laminate thickness, and A_r and ρ_r are the areal (204 g/m²) and bulk (1.76 g/cm³) reinforcement densities respectively.[28] The average laminate thickness was determined from $n=8$ measurements. The reported uncertainty represents the range due to thickness variation in the laminate. The void content V_v of each laminate was characterized using a polished 20 mm cross-section from each laminate. The void area was

manually identified using ImageJ software and V_v taken as the ratio of the void area to the total cross-sectional area.

$$V_f = (A_r n) / (\rho_r h) \quad (2)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Prepreg Preparation

The A-stage prepreg was prepared by functionalizing the reinforcement with microparticles then infusing DCPD into the functionalized reinforcement (Figure 3). The dip-coating procedure was developed instead of infusing a pre-mixed microparticle resin to minimize filtering of the microparticles by the reinforcement, ensuring uniform G2 distribution. T300 2x2 twill carbon fiber plies were functionalized with the PSU-G2 microparticles by dip-coating each ply individually in a suspension of PSU-G2 microparticles in deionized water. The functionalized plies were immediately removed after submersion and oven-dried at 110°C for 2h to remove moisture. Microparticles ostensibly adhere to the fiber surface through Van der Waals interactions after drying.

After drying, the functionalized reinforcement was infused with DCPD using the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) setup described in Figure 3C. Resin was infused at 50°C ($\eta \sim 1$ cp), which is above the melting temperature of the monomer ($T_m \sim 32^\circ\text{C}$), using a vacuum pressure of at -15 kPa.[27] After infusion, the preform was cooled to room temperature to solidify the DCPD monomer and allow the 5-ply prepreg to be removed from the bagging as a self-supporting solid—unlike liquid DCPD resin, which would immediately de-wet the reinforcement. The molar ratio of G2:DCPD, or resin formulation, was calculated from the G2 and DCPD masses added during dip-coating and infusion, respectively.

Figure 3. Prepreg Preparation and Curing. Optical and SEM images of reinforcement (A) before and (B) after dip-coating in an aqueous suspension of 5wt% PSU-G2 microparticles. Scale bars 1 cm (black) and 10 μm (white). (C) Schematic of the VARTM infusion of endo-DCPD into PSU-G2 functionalized reinforcement at 50°C to manufacture the A-stage prepreg.

3.2 Reinforcement Microparticle Functionalization

Unlike traditional prepreg processes, this manufacturing scheme introduces the polymerization initiator (G2) and monomer (DCPD) into the reinforcement in subsequent steps: reinforcement functionalization with catalyst microparticles followed by monomer infusion. Consequently, accurately predicting the final resin formulation, defined here as the molar ratio of initiator to monomer, is essential. We investigated the feasibility of this two-step approach in controlling resin formulation by systematically characterizing the dip-coating process.

The aqueous dip-coating procedure delivered reproducible and predictable microparticle uptake by the carbon fiber plies, enabling precise control of the final resin composition. The microparticle mass gain in the reinforcement increased linearly with the microparticle concentration in the dip-coating suspension (Figure 4A), consistent with prior work using different microparticles and reinforcement.[31] Notably, the trend was independent of the G2 loading within the microparticles. Using this data and the mass of DCPD added during infusion, we calculated resin formulation in the prepreg (Figure 4B). The resulting linear relationship allows prediction of the dip-coating suspension concentration needed to achieve a desired resin formulation. However, the predictive power is limited to A-stage DCPD prepregs of identical reinforcement architecture and microparticle composition.

We generalized this relationship for microparticles of arbitrary G2 loading. Since microparticle uptake (Figure 4A) is independent of G2 loading, the linear fit of resin formulation for microparticles containing 0.024 G2/PSU (Figure 4B, blue) can be scaled for other G2/PSU loadings by multiplying by the ratio $x/0.024$ where x is the G2/PSU mass ratio of interest. We validated this approach by targeting 100 ppm G2:DCPD using microparticles with 0.042 G2/PSU. The target ratio of 100 ppm was selected as this formulation has been extensively studied for phosphite inhibited pDCPD composites.[16-21] The calculated suspension concentration of 1.0 wt% PSU-G2 indeed resulted in 100 ± 10 ppm G2:DCPD after infusion (Figure 4B, orange). This demonstrates a single set of experiments (Figure 4, blue) can be extended to predict resin formulation for any G2 loading in PSU microparticles. However, additional studies are required to evaluate the effect of reinforcement architecture for further generalization.

Figure 4. Prepreg Resin Formulation. (A) The PSU-G2 microparticle mass gained by the fabric plies during dip-coating as a function of suspension concentration for microparticles containing different G2 loading. Error bars represent one standard deviation on the mean ($n=5$). (B) Corresponding resin formulation calculated using the PSU-G2 mass gain in (A), the G2/PSU ratio in the microparticles, and the mass of resin infused into the reinforcement. Error bars represent measurement uncertainty due to mass loss during handling. Pink lines represent linear fits of the data for microparticles containing 0.024 G2/PSU (blue). Orange data points represent the prepreg used in the longitudinal study for which the suspension concentration was determined using (A) to achieve a target formulation of 100 ppm G2 using microparticles containing 0.042 G2/PSU.

3.3 Prepreg Stability

As an initial probe of the prepreg's stability, we examined the resin retention over time. Immediately after infusion, a prepreg sample was removed from the vacuum bagging material and stored in a heat-sealed polyethylene (PE) bag at ambient conditions. After 14 days in the PE bag at room temperature and pressure, 85% of the resin mass was lost (Figure 5A). We attribute this to the volatilization of DCPD monomer, given its moderate vapor pressure of 1.4 mm Hg at 20°C.[32] A systematic study using neat DCPD (Figure 5B) confirmed PE's permeability to DCPD vapor as 20% of the mass was lost within 8 days. However, a typical nylon vacuum bag with sealant tape effectively retained DCPD for the same duration and was used for subsequent longitudinal testing (Figure 5C). In contrast, typical DCPD-based resins that are liquid at room temperature immediately de-wet the reinforcement during re-pressurization and debagging after infusion, prohibiting storage at ambient conditions for any length of time. DCPD's volatility underscores the need for low-volatility monomers, though this limitation can be mitigated by packaging the prepreg in DCPD-impermeable materials.

Figure 5. Prepreg Packaging. (A) A prepreg sample after 14 days stored at room temperature in a polyethylene (PE) bag with 85% of the initial resin mass lost to volatilization. (B) A sample of solid endo-DCPD monomer without reinforcement or PSU-G2 used to examine the permeability of packaging materials to volatile DCPD. (C) Comparison of DCPD mass loss in heat-sealed PE and a typical tape-sealed nylon vacuum bag. The tape-sealed nylon bag was used for the longitudinal study.

3.4 Longitudinal Study

The stability of the A-stage prepreg was evaluated through a 30-day longitudinal study examining properties of both the uncured prepreg and a frontally cured composite manufactured at each time point. After manufacturing prepreg, four 50-mm square coupons were cut to size with a rotary cutter and individually packed in a fresh nylon vacuum bag with sealant tape. The thermochemical properties of the prepreg coupons were characterized by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) after storage at room temperature and atmospheric pressure for 0, 7, 14, and 30 days. At each time point the remaining prepreg material was used to frontally cure a laminate (Figure 6A). The coupons were first consolidated using 345 kPa applied by a hand press before FC was initiated through the thickness of the laminate by a resistive heater (Omega Engineering, 10W/in²). The curing trigger consisted of a 2.5-min ramp to 180°C followed by a 2.5-min hold at 180°C controlled by a custom Arduino-Uno-based PID. A representative thermal profile measured by the thermocouple during curing is reported in Figure 6B. The cured prepreg coupons (Figure 6C) achieve excellent fiber distribution (Figure 6D).

Figure 6. Prepreg Curing. (A) Schematic of through-thickness frontal curing of the A-stage prepreg with external consolidation from a press. (B) A representative temperature profile measured by the thermocouple during the applied cure cycle. (C) A representative cured composite coupon from the A-stage prepreg and (D) corresponding optical micrograph with voids false colored in red ($V_v=0.5\%$). Scale bars 1 cm (white) and 100 μm (black).

The A-stage prepreg maintained $\alpha < 20\%$ and frontally cured to achieve $\alpha > 99\%$ at all time points in the 1-month study (Figure 7A). This demonstrates the stability of this system compared to B-staged DCPD prepreps, which reach $\alpha > 20\%$ within 2 to 4 hours at room temperature.[24] Once cured, the prepreg coupons achieved robust properties summarized in Table 1; the laminates exhibited fiber volume fractions approaching 50% and low void fractions near 2%. The variation in constituents is attributed to variability in hand-pressing and the absence of vacuum during curing. Thermomechanical characterization (Figure 7B) showed glass transition temperatures T_g near 160°C with variation in the storage modulus again attributed to nonuniform consolidation causing local thickness and V_f variation. The extracted fraction of each laminate approximates the maximum possible mass loss due to vacuum in space (Table 1). While not a substitute for standardized thermal vacuum (TVAC) characterization, the screening approach provides valuable insights into the monomer incorporation beyond DSC. Mass loss remained below 2% at each time point, an encouraging preliminary indication of the material’s off-gassing stability once cured. Overall, the longitudinal study confirms A-stage retains reactivity when properly packaged as well as its capacity to form high-performance composites via rapid, energy-efficient frontal curing.

Storage time [days]	V_f [%]	V_v [%]	T_g [°C]	Extracted mass [wt%]
0	46 ± 5	2 ± 1	160 ± 1	1.0 ± 0.3
7	48 ± 5	2 ± 1	153 ± 1	1.8 ± 0.6
14	45 ± 6	4 ± 1	163 ± 1	1.5 ± 0.4
30	49 ± 6	2 ± 1	166 ± 2	1.8 ± 0.4

Table 1: Properties of Cured Prepreg Coupons.

Figure 7. Longitudinal Study. (A) The degree of cure measured by DSC for prepreg after storage at room temperature in nylon bagging before and after frontal curing. (B) Representative DMA curves for laminates manufactured from prepreg after storage for 0 to 30 days at room temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We developed a novel A-staging approach to create a shelf-stable, frontally curable prepreg by physically separating reactive components. Through microencapsulation of the polymerization initiator coupled with unreacted (A-stage) monomer that is solid at room temperature, the A-stage microparticle prepreg achieves long-term stability. We developed a two-step dip-coating and infusion process to manufacture the unique prepreg. Systematic variation of microparticle concentration in the aqueous dip-coating suspension enabled tunable initiator loading on the reinforcement. Importantly, we demonstrated control over the resin formulation by achieving a target initiator-monomer ratio in the final prepreg despite introducing the initiator and monomer in separate processes. The use of solid monomer prevents de-wetting immediately after infusion, though the monomer volatility necessitates careful packaging to prevent de-wetting during long-term storage. When properly packaged, the prepreg retains degree of cure under 20% over one month and successfully undergoes frontal curing, yielding a high-quality composite. The A-stage prepreg method developed in this work represents a 300-fold increase in shelf life over previously reported B-staged frontally curable DCPD prepreps. The A-stage prepreg's combination of months-long stability; low-energy, on-demand curing; and robust composite properties addresses the unique challenges of large-scale in-space manufacturing and marks a pivotal advancement in the viability of composite manufacturing via frontally curable prepreps.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support from DARPA, United States as part of the NOM4D program through Award HR001122C0057. The authors thank the Imaging Technology Group at the Beckman Institute for Advanced Science and Technology and the School of Chemical Sciences NMR laboratory at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign for the facilities necessary to complete this work. The authors thank Dr. Zhenchuang Xu for his assistance in conducting NMR experiments. T. Price thanks the Arnold and Mabel Beckman Foundation for financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Xue, J. Liu, C. Wu and Y. Tong, Review of in-space assembly technologies, *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, **34**, 2021, pp. 21–47 (doi: 10.1016/j.cja.2020.09.043).
- [2] NASA Office of Inspector General, *NASA's Management of the International Space Station and Efforts to Commercialize Low Earth Orbit*, IG-22-005, NASA, 2021.
- [3] E. Gibney, How to build a Moon base, *Nature*, **562**, 2018, pp. 474–478 (doi: 10.1038/d41586-018-07107-4).

- [4] H. G. Bhundiya, F. Royer and Z. Cordero, Engineering Framework for Assessing Materials and Processes for In-Space Manufacturing, *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, **31**, 2022, pp. 6045–6059 (doi: 10.1007/s11665-022-06755-y).
- [5] NASA Technical Library Branch, *Technology for Large Space Systems*, SP_7046(20), NASA, 1989.
- [6] I.M. Daniel and O. Ishai, *Engineering mechanics of composite materials*, Oxford University Press, New York, 2006.
- [7] K. Tserpes and I. Sioutis, Advances in Composite Materials for Space Applications: A Comprehensive Literature Review, *Aerospace*, **12**, 2025, pp. 215 (doi: 10.3390/aerospace12030215).
- [8] T. G. Gutowski, *Advanced composites manufacturing*, Wiley, New York, 1997.
- [9] Clyne, T. W. and D. Hull, *An introduction to composite materials*, Cambridge University Press, New York, 2019.
- [10] Toray Composite Materials America Inc., *3960 Prepreg System Product Data Sheet*, 2025.
- [11] Hexcel Corporation, *HexPly M21 Product Data Sheet*, 2020.
- [12] Hexcel Corporation, *HexPly M77HF Product Data Sheet*, 2022.
- [13] B.A. Suslick, J. Hemmer, B. R. Groce, K. J. Stawiasz, P. H. Geubelle, G. Malucelli, A. Mariani, J. S. Moore, J. A. Pojman and N. R. Sottos, Frontal Polymerizations: From Chemical Perspectives to Macroscopic Properties and Applications, *Chemical Reviews*, **123**, 2023, pp. 3237–3298 (doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.2c00686).
- [14] J. A. Pojman, Cure-on-Demand Composites by Frontal Polymerization, *Encyclopedia of Materials: Plastics and Polymers*, 2022.
- [15] D. Bomze, P. Knaack, T. Koch, H. Jin and R. Liska, Radical induced cationic frontal polymerization as a versatile tool for epoxy curing and composite production, *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*, **54**, 2016, pp. 3751–3759 (doi: 10.1002/pola.28274).
- [16] I.D. Robertson, M. Yourdkhani, P. J. Centellas, J. E. Aw, D. G. Ivanoff, E. Goli, E. M. Lloyd, L. M. Dean, N. R. Sottos, P. H. Geubelle, J. S. Moore and S. R. White, Rapid energy-efficient manufacturing of polymers and composites via frontal polymerization, *Nature*, **557**, 2018, pp. 223–227 (doi: 10.1038/s41586-018-0054-x).
- [17] P.J. Centellas, M. Yourdkhani, S. Vyas, B. Koohbor, P. H. Geubelle and N. R. Sottos, Rapid multiple-front polymerization of fiber-reinforced polymer composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **158**, 2022, pp. 106931 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2022.106931).
- [18] I. Naseri and M. Yourdkhani, Rapid and Energy-Efficient Frontal Curing of Multifunctional Composites Using Integrated Nanostructured Heaters, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, **14**, 2022, pp. 50215–50224 (doi: 10.1021/acsami.2c15415).
- [19] C. Dojan, M. Ziaee, S. Radosevich and M. Yourdkhani, Additive Manufacturing of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Thermoset Composites via In-Situ Thermal Curing, *Nature Communications*, **16**, 2025, (doi: 10.1038/s41467-025-59848-2).
- [20] P. Centellas, M. Garg, Z. Chen, X. Zhang, N. Parikh, P. Geubelle and N. Sottos, Energy-efficient manufacturing of multifunctional vascularized composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **57**, 2022, pp. 581–592 (doi: 10.1177/00219983221142353).
- [21] S. Vyas, N. A. Parikh, T. C. Price, D. P. Patel, T. B. Le, P. H. Geubelle and N. R. Sottos, Through-thickness frontal polymerization: Process development and optimization, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **180**, 2024, pp. 108084 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108084).
- [22] E. Goli, N. A. Parikh, M. Yourdkhani, N. G. Hibbard, J. S. Moore, N. R. Sottos and P. H. Geubelle, Frontal polymerization of unidirectional carbon-fiber-reinforced composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **130**, 2020, p. 105689 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.105689).
- [23] N. S. Hmeidat, M. Zakoworotony, Y. S. Kim, T. B. Le, G. DeBrun, R. Shah, J. J. Lessard, J. S. Moore, J. W. Baur, P. H. Geubelle, N. R. Sottos and S. H. Tawfick, Reactive extrusion of frontally polymerizing continuous carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites, *Composites*

- Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **190**, 2025, pp. 108609 (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108609)
- [24] N.A. Parikh, *Rapid Manufacturing of Thermoset Polymers and Composites Processed by Frontal Polymerization*, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, 2023.
- [25] I.D. Robertson, L. M. Dean, G. E. Rudebusch, N. R. Sottos, S. R. White and J. S. Moore, Alkyl Phosphite Inhibitors for Frontal Ring-Opening Metathesis Polymerization Greatly Increase Pot Life, *ACS Macro Letters*, **6**, 2017, pp. 609–612 (doi: 10.1021/acsmacrolett.7b00270).
- [26] O. Davydovich, A. J. Greenlee, H. D. Root, A. L. Jansen, S. C. Gallegos, M. J. Warner, M. S. Kent, J. A. Cardenas, L. N. Appelhans, D. J. Roach, B. H. Jones and S. C. Leguizamon, Encapsulated Transition Metal Catalysts Enable Long-term Stability in Frontal Polymerization Resins, *Macromolecules*, **56**, 2023, pp. 7543–7550 (doi: 10.1021/acs.macromol.3c01146).
- [27] I. Palmová, J. Kosek, J. Schöngut, M. Marek, and K. Štěpánek, Experimental and modeling studies of oligomerization and copolymerization of dicyclopentadiene, *Chemical Engineering Science*, **56**, 2001, pp. 927–935 (doi: 10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00307-9).
- [28] ASTM D30 Committee, *ASTM D3171 Test Methods for Constituent Content of Composite Materials*, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2022.
- [29] Pastore, R., A. Delfini, M. Albano, A. Vricella, M. Marchetti, F. Santoni and F. Piergentili, Outgassing effect in polymeric composites exposed to space environment thermal-vacuum conditions, *Acta Astronautica*, **170**, 2020, pp., 466–471 (doi: 10.1016/j.actaastro.2020.02.019).
- [30] ASTM D30 Committee, *ASTM C613 Test Method for Constituent Content of Composite Prepreg by Soxhlet Extraction*, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2019.
- [31] Y.S. Kim, A. R. Jones, N. R. Sottos and S. R. White, Manufacturing of unidirectional glass/epoxy prepreg with microencapsulated liquid healing agents, *Composites Science and Technology*, **153**, 2017, pp. 190–197 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.10.017).
- [32] T. E. Daubert and R. P. Danner, *Physical and thermodynamic properties of pure chemicals: data compilation*. CRC Press, 1989.

International Committee on Composite Materials

Student Status Confirmation Form for the ICCM Tsai Award

May 1, 2025

I, Nancy Sottos, hereby confirm that Tyler Price, who applied for the ICCM Tsai Award, was, at the date of the abstract submission 12/10/24, a PhD student under my supervision at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.

Nancy Sottos
Department Head and Swanlund Chair
University of Illinois
Materials Science & Engineering
1304 W. Green Street
Urbana, IL 61801
217-333-1031
n-sottos@illinois.edu

Authors Contributions

Manuscript title: Prepreg Development for Rapid On-Orbit Composites Manufacturing via Frontal Curing

Please describe the contributions of each author, referring to the taxonomy below.

Author 1 (Tsai Award Applicant): Tyler Price

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
conducted the analyses of the microparticle size distribution (Fig. 2), dip-coating (Fig. 4), packaging (Fig. 5), and longitudinal study (Fig. 6-7; Table 1) data and contributed to the analysis of the nmr data.
- Investigation**
Conducted manufacturing, dip-coating, infusion, packaging, and longitudinal studies.
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Validation**
Verified reproducibility of the prepreg manufacturing/curing and select time points in the longitudinal study.
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author 2: Po-Wen Wang

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Contributed to the analysis of the nmr data (Fig. 2)
- Investigation**
Manufactured catalyst microparticles and conducted SEM imaging.
- Methodology**
Developed the methodology to manufacture catalyst-containing microparticles.
- Software**
Contributed to the development of the microparticle SEM image analysis software.
- Validation**
Conducted validation of the microparticle identification software by manual analysis.
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author 4: Jeffrey Moore

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Validation**

- Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author 5: Sameh Tawfick

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
Contributed to the development of the microparticle SEM image analysis software.
- Validation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author 6: Nancy Sottos

- Conception**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Data curation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)

- Formal Analysis**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Investigation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Methodology**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Software**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Validation**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Visualization**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (original draft)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Wrote the paper (review and editing)**
Specify contribution in more detail (optional; no more than one sentence)
- Other contribution**
Specify contribution in more detail (required; no more than one sentence)

Author Signatures

Tyler Price

Po-Wen Wang

Jeffrey Moore

Sameh Tawfick

Nancy Sottos

Conceptualization

Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.

Data Curation

Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse.

Formal Analysis

Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data.

Investigation

Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.

Methodology

Development or design of methodology; creation of models.

Software

Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.

Validation

Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.

Visualization

Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.

Writing – Original Draft Preparation

Creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).

Writing – Review & Editing

Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.